

Testing Scenario

A. Testing on Cisco

1. Interoperability Test

a. Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

- Cisco Connectivity Test

```
VPN-Site>ping 172.16.220.10  
Type escape sequence to abort.  
Sending 5, 100-byte ICMP Echos to 172.16.220.10, timeout is 2 seconds:  
!!!!  
Success rate is 100 percent (5/5), round-trip min/avg/max = 1/1/4 ms
```

Figure Cisco Connectivity Test

Figure shows the results of a connectivity test using the ping command from the Cisco device to IP address 172.16.220.10. The ping result indicates a success rate of 100% (5/5 packets) with a minimum/average/maximum round-trip time of 1/1/4 ms, showing no packet loss.

b. Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

The test was carried out using the ping command from Site A (Cisco) to Site B (Cisco).

```
C:\Users\Administrator>ping 172.16.58.10  
Pinging 172.16.58.10 with 32 bytes of data:  
Reply from 172.16.58.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126  
Reply from 172.16.58.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126  
Reply from 172.16.58.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126  
Reply from 172.16.58.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
```

Figure Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

The figure shows the results of the connectivity test using the ping command from Site A to Site B with the destination address 172.16.58.10. The consistent responses demonstrate that the VPN tunnel between the two sites has been successfully established and is functioning properly, enabling smooth data communication between Site A and Site B on the Cisco platform.

Based on the figure, the analysis results using Wireshark on the Cisco platform successfully demonstrate the implementation of AES encryption on traffic passing through the VPN tunnel. In the packet capture test, no plaintext data (readable text) was found, confirming that all data communication has been successfully encrypted. This verifies that the security configuration of the VPN tunnel on all platforms has been effectively implemented in securing data transmission between sites.

3. Quality of Service (QoS) Testing

a. Throughput Calculation

The formula used is as follows:

$$\text{Throughput}(kb) = \frac{\text{Package Received}(kb)}{\text{Delivery Time}(s)}$$

Interfaces				
Interface	Dropped packets	Capture filter	Link type	Packet size limit (snaplen)
Ethernet 3	0 (0.0%)	none	Ethernet	262144 bytes
Statistics				
Measurement	Captured	Displayed	Marked	
Packets	21202	21202 (100.0%)	—	
Time span, s	10.993	10.993	—	
Average pps	1928.6	1928.6	—	
Average packet size, B	2181	2181	—	
Bytes	46239609	46239609 (100.0%)	0	
Average bytes/s	4206 k	4206 k	—	
Average bits/s	33 M	33 M	—	

Figure Wireshark Statistics Capture on Cisco

Based on the figure, the throughput value can be calculated as follows:

Total bytes transferred: 46239609 bytes

Time span: 10.993 seconds

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{46239609}{10.99} = 4.206.277 \text{ bytes}$$

b. Packet Loss

From the Wireshark statistics on Cisco in Figure, it can be seen on the Ethernet 3 interface that the dropped packets are 0.0%.

c. Delay/Latency

The formula used is as follows:

$$\text{Delay}(ms) = \frac{\text{Total delay}(s)}{\text{Package Received}(kb)}$$

- Total Delay : 10.993337 detik
- Received packets : 21202

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Delay} &= \frac{10.993337}{21202} = 0.000518505 \text{ s} \\ &= 0.518504717 \text{ ms} \end{aligned}$$

d. Jitter

The formula used is as follows:

$$jitter(ms) = \frac{total\ Variation\ of\ Delay\ (s)}{Package\ Received(kb)}$$

Total delay variation: 0.001223 seconds

Received packets: 21202

$$\begin{aligned} Jitter &= \frac{0.001223}{21202} = 0.00000006\text{ s} \\ &= 0.00005768\text{ ms} \end{aligned}$$

B. Testing on MikroTik

1. Interoperability Test

a. Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

- MikroTik Connectivity Test


```
Terminal <1>
/          Move up to base level
..        Move up one level
/command  Use command at the base level
aug/27/2024 08:07:57 system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 172.1
6.58.10 via winbox
aug/27/2024 08:08:04 system,error,critical login failure for user admin from 172.1
6.58.10 via winbox
[altir-iradmin@MikroTik] > ping 172.16.220.10
[SEQ HOST                                SIZE TTL TIME  STATUS
0 172.16.220.10                          56 126 1ms   SUCCESS
1 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
2 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
3 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
4 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
5 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
6 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
7 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
8 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
9 172.16.220.10                          56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
10 172.16.220.10                         56 126 0ms   SUCCESS
sent=11 received=11 packet-loss=0% min-rtt=0ms avg-rtt=0ms max-rtt=1ms
```

Figure MikroTik Connectivity Test

Figure shows the results of the connectivity test using the ping command from the MikroTik device to IP address 172.16.220.10. The test results show that 10 ping packets of 56 bytes each were successfully sent and received, with consistent response times of 12 ms per packet. This indicates that connectivity from Site A to Site B via MikroTik is functioning properly with no packet loss.

b. Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

The test was carried out using the ping command from Site A (Cisco) to Site B (MikroTik).


```
C:\Users\Administrator>ping 172.16.58.10
Pinging 172.16.58.10 with 32 bytes of data:
Reply from 172.16.58.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
```

Figure Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

The figure shows the connectivity test results from Site A (Cisco) to Site B (MikroTik) using the ping command to IP address 172.16.58.10. The successful pings prove that the VPN tunnel between the Cisco platform at Site A and MikroTik at Site B has been established and is functioning properly, enabling smooth data communication between sites.

properly encrypted. This verifies that the security configuration of the VPN tunnel across all platforms is effectively protecting data transmission between sites.

3. Quality of Service (QoS) Testing

For QoS testing on the MikroTik IPsec VPN implementation, a 50 MB FTP file transfer scenario was used.

a. Throughput Calculation

The formula used is as follows:

$$\text{Throughput}(kb) = \frac{\text{Package Received}(kb)}{\text{Delivery Time}(s)}$$

Interfaces				
Interface	Dropped packets	Capture filter	Link type	Packet size limit (snaplen)
Ethernet 3	0 (0.0%)	none	Ethernet	262144 bytes

Statistics			
Measurement	Captured	Displayed	Marked
Packets	21886	21886 (100.0%)	—
Time span, s	20.308	20.308	—
Average pps	1077.7	1077.7	—
Average packet size, B	2467	2467	—
Bytes	54000245	54000245 (100.0%)	0
Average bytes/s	2659 k	2659 k	—
Average bits/s	21 M	21 M	—

Figure Wireshark Statistics Capture on MikroTik

Based on the figure, throughput can be calculated as follows:

Total bytes transferred: 54000245 bytes

Time span: 20.308 seconds

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{54000245}{20.308} = 2,659,062 \text{ bytes}$$

b. Packet Loss

From the Wireshark statistics in Figure on the Ethernet 3 interface, dropped packets are 0.0%.

c. Delay/Latency

The formula used is as follows:

$$\text{Delay}(ms) = \frac{\text{Total delay}(s)}{\text{Package Received}(kb)}$$

Total Delay: 20.307949 detik

Package Received : 21886

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Delay} &= \frac{20.307949}{21886} = 0.000927897 \text{ s} \\ &= 0.927896783 \text{ ms} \end{aligned}$$

d. Jitter

The formula used is as follows:

$$jitter(ms) = \frac{total\ Variation\ of\ Delay\ (s)}{Package\ Received(kb)}$$

- Total Variation of Delay : 0.224891 detik
- Package Received : 21886

$$Jitter = \frac{0.224891}{21886} = 0.00001028\ s$$
$$= 0.01027556\ ms$$

B. Testing on pfSense

1. Interoperability Test

a. Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

- pfSense Connectivity Test

```
Results
PING 172.16.220.10 (172.16.220.10): 56 data bytes
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=0 ttl=126 time=0.532 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=1 ttl=126 time=0.696 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=2 ttl=126 time=0.548 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=3 ttl=126 time=0.691 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=4 ttl=126 time=0.525 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=5 ttl=126 time=0.531 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=6 ttl=126 time=0.636 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=7 ttl=126 time=0.662 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=8 ttl=126 time=0.643 ms
64 bytes from 172.16.220.10: icmp_seq=9 ttl=126 time=0.675 ms

--- 172.16.220.10 ping statistics ---
10 packets transmitted, 10 packets received, 0.0% packet loss
round-trip min/avg/max/stddev = 0.525/0.614/0.696/0.068 ms

pfSense is developed and maintained by Netgate.
```

Figure pfSense Connectivity Test

Figure shows the connectivity test results using the ping command from the pfSense device to IP address 172.16.220.10. The test results show that 10 ping packets of 64 bytes each were successfully sent and received, with a 100% success rate (0% packet loss), indicating excellent connectivity from Site A to Site B via pfSense.

b. Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

The test was carried out using the ping command from Site A (Cisco) to Site B (pfSense).

```
C:\Users\Administrator>ping 172.16.58.10

Pinging 172.16.58.10 with 32 bytes of data:
Reply from 172.16.58.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
```

Figure Connectivity Test from Site A to Site B

The figure shows the connectivity test results from Site A (Cisco) to Site B (pfSense) using the ping command to IP address 172.16.58.10. The results show that the VPN tunnel between the Cisco platform at Site A and pfSense at Site B has been successfully established and is functioning properly, allowing smooth data communication between sites.

2. Security Testing
a. Access Control Testing

```
Ethernet adapter Ethernet:  
Connection-specific DNS Suffix . . . :  
Link-local IPv6 Address . . . . . : fe80::a999:35e4:382:ae8d%20  
IPv4 Address. . . . . : 10.1.10.3  
Subnet Mask . . . . . : 255.255.255.0  
Default Gateway . . . . . : 10.1.10.2  
  
Ethernet adapter Bluetooth Network Connection:  
Media State . . . . . : Media disconnected  
Connection-specific DNS Suffix . . . :  
  
C:\Users\Administrator>ping 172.16.220.10  
  
Pinging 172.16.220.10 with 32 bytes of data:  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Request timed out.  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Request timed out.  
  
Ping statistics for 172.16.220.10:  
Packets: Sent = 4, Received = 2, Lost = 2 (50% loss),  
  
C:\Users\Administrator>ping 172.16.58.10  
  
Pinging 172.16.58.10 with 32 bytes of data:  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Request timed out.  
  
Ping statistics for 172.16.58.10:  
Packets: Sent = 4, Received = 3, Lost = 1 (25% loss),
```

Figure Access Control Test on pfSense outside the VPN Tunnel

The access control test results show that the pfSense platform successfully implemented security policies by effectively blocking all access attempts from outside the VPN tunnel. This is confirmed by the absence of responses to pings from IP addresses outside the designated network.

b. Encryption Strength Testing

Figure Encryption Strength Testing on pfSense

Based on the figure, the Wireshark analysis on the pfSense platform shows that AES encryption has been successfully implemented on traffic passing through the VPN tunnel. No plaintext data was found in the packet capture, confirming that all data communication has been properly encrypted. This verifies that the security configuration of the VPN tunnel across all platforms is effective in protecting data transmission between sites.

3. Quality of Service (QoS) Testing

For the QoS test on pfSense's IPsec VPN implementation, a 50 MB FTP file transfer scenario was used.

a. Throughput Calculation

The formula used is as follows:

$$\text{Throughput}(kb) = \frac{\text{Package Received}(kb)}{\text{Delivery Time}(s)}$$

The screenshot shows the Wireshark Statistics window for a capture on pfSense. It is divided into two main sections: 'Interfaces' and 'Statistics'.

Interfaces				
Interface	Dropped packets	Capture filter	Link type	Packet size limit (snaplen)
Ethernet 3	0 (0.0%)	none	Ethernet	262144 bytes

Statistics				
Measurement	Captured	Displayed	Marked	
Packets	40124	40041 (99.8%)	—	
Time span, s	65.766	65.766	—	
Average pps	610.1	608.8	—	
Average packet size, B	1389	1392	—	
Bytes	55748921	55725012 (100.0%)	0	
Average bytes/s	847 k	847 k	—	
Average bits/s	6781 k	6778 k	—	

Figure Wireshark Statistics Capture on pfSense

Based on the figure, throughput can be calculated as follows:

Total bytes transferred: 55748921 bytes

Time span: 65.766 seconds

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{55748921}{65.766} = 847,686 \text{ bytes}$$

b. Packet Loss

From the Wireshark statistics on pfSense in Figure 4.32, dropped packets are 0.0%.

c. Delay/Latency

The formula used is as follows:

$$\text{Delay}(ms) = \frac{\text{Total delay}(s)}{\text{Package Received}(kb)}$$

Total Delay: 61.314421 detik

Package Received : 39473

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Delay} &= \frac{61.314421}{39473} = 0.001553326 \text{ s} \\ &= 1.55332559 \text{ ms} \end{aligned}$$

d. Jitter

$$jitter(ms) = \frac{\text{total Variation of Delay (s)}}{\text{Package Received(kb)}}$$

total Variation of Delay : 0.099211 detik

Package Received : 39473

$$\begin{aligned} Jitter &= \frac{0.099211}{39473} = 0.00000251 \text{ s} \\ &= 0.00251339 \text{ ms} \end{aligned}$$

D. Testing on OPNsense

1. Interoperability Testing

a. Site A to Site B Connectivity Testing

- OPNsense Connectivity Test

<input type="checkbox"/> IP	MAC	Manufacturer
<input type="checkbox"/> 10.1.10.1	48:4d:7e:b2:5d:78	Dell Inc.
<input type="checkbox"/> 10.1.10.2	00:0a:b8:4c:e8:94	Cisco Systems, Inc
<input type="checkbox"/> 172.16.58.1	00:e0:6c:6d:6d:ca	Ultra Electronics Command & Control Systems
<input type="checkbox"/> 172.16.58.10	54:48:10:e4:27:2e	Dell Inc.


```
Command Prompt

Pinging 172.16.220.10 with 32 bytes of data:
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=1ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=1ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=1ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=1ms TTL=126
Reply from 172.16.220.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126

Ping statistics for 172.16.220.10:
    Packets: Sent = 10, Received = 10, Lost = 0 (0% loss),
    Approximate round trip times in milli-seconds:
        Minimum = 1ms, Maximum = 2ms, Average = 1ms
```

Figure OPNsense Connectivity Test

b. Site A to Site B Connectivity Testing

The testing was conducted by performing a ping test from Site A (Cisco) to Site B (pfSense).

```
C:\Users\Administrator>ping 172.16.58.10

Pinging 172.16.58.10 with 32 bytes of data:
Reply from 172.16.58.10: bytes=32 time=2ms TTL=126
```

Figure Site A to Site B Connectivity Test

The results of the interoperability testing show that the MikroTik platform successfully established a VPN tunnel with Site A.

2. Security Testing
a. Access Control Testing

```
Ethernet adapter Ethernet:  
Connection-specific DNS Suffix . :  
Link-Local IPv6 Address . . . . . : fe80::a999:35e4:382:ae8d%20  
IPv4 Address. . . . . : 10.1.10.3  
Subnet Mask . . . . . : 255.255.255.0  
Default Gateway . . . . . : 10.1.10.2  
  
Ethernet adapter Bluetooth Network Connection:  
Media State . . . . . : Media disconnected  
Connection-specific DNS Suffix . :  
  
C:\Users\Administrator>ping 172.16.220.10  
  
Pinging 172.16.220.10 with 32 bytes of data:  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Request timed out.  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Request timed out.  
  
Ping statistics for 172.16.220.10:  
Packets: Sent = 4, Received = 2, Lost = 2 (50% loss),  
  
C:\Users\Administrator>ping 172.16.58.10  
  
Pinging 172.16.58.10 with 32 bytes of data:  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Reply from 10.1.10.3: Destination host unreachable.  
Request timed out.  
  
Ping statistics for 172.16.58.10:  
Packets: Sent = 4, Received = 3, Lost = 1 (25% loss),
```

Figure Access Control Testing on OPNsense Outside the VPN Tunnel

The results of the access control testing show that the OPNsense platform successfully implemented the security policy. The platform effectively blocked any access attempts originating from outside the designated VPN tunnel. This was confirmed by the absence of responses to ping tests from IP addresses outside the predetermined network.

b. Encryption Strength Testing

Figure Encryption Strength Testing on OPNsense

Based on the above figure, the results of the analysis using Wireshark show that the OPNsense platform successfully implemented AES encryption on the traffic passing through the VPN tunnel. In the packet capture testing, no data in plaintext (readable text) was found, confirming that all data communication was successfully encrypted. This verifies that the security configuration of the VPN tunnel on all platforms has functioned effectively in securing data transmission between sites.

3. Quality of Service (QoS) Testing

a. Throughput Calculation

The formula used to calculate throughput is as follows:

$$\text{Throughput}(kb) = \frac{\text{Package Received}(kb)}{\text{Delivery Time}(s)}$$

Interfaces				
Interface	Dropped packets	Capture filter	Link type	Packet size limit (snaplen)
Ethernet 3	0 (0.0%)	none	Ethernet	262144 bytes
Statistics				
Measurement	Captured	Displayed	Marked	
Packets	38740	38740 (100.0%)	—	
Time span, s	65.870	65.870	—	
Average pps	588.1	588.1	—	
Average packet size, B	1431	1431	—	
Bytes	55448116	55448116 (100.0%)	0	
Average bytes/s	841 k	841 k	—	
Average bits/s	6734 k	6734 k	—	

Figure Capture of OPNsense Statistics from Wireshark

Based on the above figure, the throughput value can be calculated as follows:

Total bytes transferred: 55448116 bytes

Time span: 65.870 seconds

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{55448116}{65.870} = 841,781 \text{ bytes}$$

b. Packet Loss

From the OPNsense Wireshark statistics in Figure, it can be seen that on the Ethernet Interface 3, the dropped packets are 0.0%.

c. Delay/Latency

The formula used is as follows:

$$\text{Delay}(ms) = \frac{\text{Total delay}(s)}{\text{Package Received}(kb)}$$

Total Delay: 61.314421 detik

Paket data diterima : 39473

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Delay} &= \frac{61.314421}{39473} = 0.001553326 \text{ s} \\ &= 1.55332559 \text{ ms} \end{aligned}$$

d. Jitter

The formula used is as follows:

$$jitter(ms) = \frac{\text{total Variation of Delay (s)}}{\text{Package Received(kb)}}$$

total Variation of Delay : 0.099211 detik

Package Received : 39473

$$\begin{aligned} Jitter &= \frac{0.099211}{39473} = 0.00000251 \text{ s} \\ &= 0.08766733\text{ms} \end{aligned}$$